

JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX

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ANNOTATION

This JAVA programming in the article OYD is indispensable in the language part has been heritage to do Heritage to do syntax and semantics cause passed . Heritage to do circle issues and their software supply

Key words : class, string, currency

ANNOTATION

In this article, inheritance is an integral part of the JAVA programming language. Syntax and semantics of inheritance are mentioned . Legacy issues and their software

Keywords: class, string, currency

Heritage do - JAVA's and of the MOON each how of the language indispensable part _ Heritage to do syntax composition from the syntax much more complicated . You class heritage by doing while taking , you like " Here my new my class , this while old to the object like " like " . you will be You this program in the code show - you , as usual , class name you give , but circle brackets from opening before you extend key the word you write , then fatherhood class the name This while you're doing it your new your class fatherhood of the class all informative contents and styles automatic way takes _

```
class Person {  
    String name;  
    String firstName;  
    int age;  
    String get Name ( ) {...}  
    String geted ( ) {...}  
}  
class Student extends Person {  
    String Studid ;  
    String geted ( ) {...}  
    String get Courses ( ) {...}  
}
```



```
class Employee extends Person {
    Currency Salary;
    String get Salary ( ) {...}
}
```

Heritage by get semantics .

But we are children from class object want to make in fact _ suddenly two class object - paternity (basic) and childhood , was new our object show a little more complicated will be External this so to look has : new class the same so interface , as is paternal , and perhaps one how many new style and to the khoshiyas

Owner but this there is fatherhood class simply copy it's not . You childhood class when you compile , compiled object so fatherhood has an " object " of the class will be But this object under class object inside hidden will be That's why for in the object this object the bottom initialization very important is considered This object of initialization constructor inside is initialization because class fatherhood class about everyone data and to benefits have _ That's why for JAVA bro class constructor into automatic way puts _ Heritage by doing in getting relation as " Contains " . will be

Class below opportunities .

Heritage by doing received fatherhood style again determination have a chance . (in our example - goted) but in this style name , style basics immutability must be returned the parameters are also the same different to be need _

An example karab let's go :

```
class Car Wash {
    private Strings = new String("Car Wash"),
    public void append(String a) {s += a;}
    public void wash ( ) {append ("wash the car");}
    public void foam ( ) {append("foam the car");}
    public void dry ( ) {append("dry the car");}
    public void printProtocol ( ) { System . out . println (S); }
    public static void main (String args [ ]) {
        Car wash CW = new Car wash ( );
        CW foam ( ); CW wash ( ); CW dry ( );
        CW printProtocol ( );
    }
```


}

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